

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A575

14 September 1997

ACSOE

Investigation of Tropical Air
originating over the US

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 4575

Date: 14/9/97

A/S Name: H. ROBERT

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for *SEVERAL FOR MENE*
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period *INDEF*
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project *ALLIANCE ACSE*
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? *INDEF*
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept? *NOT USED*
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

A575 ACSOE SCIENCE

September 14, 1997

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To observe the atmospheric chemical composition in atlantic air Southwest of the Azores. The data will be added to a systematically collected airmass data base and will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere. It is hoped that we will be able to intercept air which has stratospheric characteristics during the transit.

LOCATION:

Northeast Atlantic Ocean, Southwest of the Azores.

WEATHER:

Cloud Free

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart airfield and transit to oceanic airspace.
 - [1.1] Hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check. *← NOxy CAL 15mins FL200*
- [2] Stepped profile from 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) to FL200 — 500ft/min to top of boundary layer then 1000ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200
- [2.1] Run for NOxy Calibration.
- [3] Sawtooth to top of next profile location.
- [4] Stepped profile from FL200 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) — 1000ft/min to top of boundary layer then 500ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200
- [5] Stepped profile from 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) to FL200 — 500ft/min to top of boundary layer then 1000ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200
- [6] Sawtooth to top of next profile location. ✓
- [7] Stepped profile from FL200 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) — 1000ft/min to top of boundary layer then 500ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200

- [8] Stepped profile from 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) to FL200 — 500ft/min to top of boundary layer then 1000ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200
- [9] Run to top of next profile location.
- [10] Stepped profile from FL200 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) — 1000ft/min to top of boundary layer then 500ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200
- [11] Stepped profile from 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) to FL200 — 500ft/min to top of boundary layer then 1000ft/min.
Fill bottles at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, FL070, FL150, FL200
- [12] Sawtooth to top of next profile location.
- [13] Profile into Santa Maria from FL200.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure and temperature to be kept constant on level runs. The NOxy should ideally be zeroed every 15 minutes. During profiles this should be done at the start of grab sample runs. Other instrument operators should perform zeros at this time if required.

TIME:

hours.

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. AS75

Date 14/9/97

Sheet no. 4/2

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
37	R 38			FL 130	185200	185532	185703	622	1 min purge 6.9 bar
38	R 42			FL 150	185800	190005	190229		1 min purge 6 bar
39	H 3			FL 180	190346	190640	190832	509	1 min purge 5.8 bar
40	S/S			FL 220	191000	191346	191615	430	

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

 Flight No. AS75

 Date 14/3/97

 Sheet no. 3/4

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
25	R 19			5000'	170100	170712	170748	847	3 min purge on run 7 bar
26	R 25			500'	171000	171728	171755	994	1 min purge on run 7 bar.
27	S 11			100'	171800	172010	172032	1013	no purge on run. P7.
28	R 37			5000'	172200	173052	173124	846	1 min purge 7
29	R 4			FL 100	173400	174004	174052	700	1 min purge 7
30	R 36			FL 130	174200	174700	174830	622	1 min purge. 7 bar
31	S 16			FL 150	175000	175245	175411	572	1 min purge 6.5 bar
32	R 32			FL 180	175600	175901	180112	506	1 min purge 5.8 bar.
33	A 8			FL 220	180245	181013	181306	420	4.9 bar
34	R 13			PB 500'	182000	182960	183041		1 min purge 500 5000 100 7 bar
35	R 16			5000'	183300	184100	18418	847	1 min purge 130 - 7 bar 150
36	R 9			FL 100	184300	184849	184952	700	7 bar 180 200

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. 4575

Date 14/3/97

Sheet no. 2/4

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE		True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
					PRGE TIME	FILL TIME		
13	S/4			100'	14403	144100		P3 7 bar
14	S/12			500'	144250	144324		1 min purge only total 7 bar
15	4/9			1000'	144450	144610	144642	1 min purge on run only Fill from run start.
16	4/7			3000'	144755	14533	145400	3 min purge on run
17	S/09 1*			FL 070	145445	150134	150210	1 min purge on run * ex Harwell
18	4/11			FL 150	150500	151250	151432	1 min purge on run. 6.5 bar.
19	S/3			FL 200	151600	152600	152907	5.4 bar.
20	S/8			FL 200	161500	163010	163310	before P6 on run 5. 4 to 9 bar only
21	2/2			FL 180	163500	163855	164148	504 after 1 min purge on run
22	S/7			FL 150	164342	164630	164838	573 1 min purge on run 150 130 200 500
23	S/9			FL 130	164944	165220	165342	528 1 min on purge on run 500 7. bar 50
24	S/10			FL 100	165513	165822	165911	700 1 min purp on run 7 bar

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

G.C. Form 2

Flight no. A575

Date 14 9 97

Sheet no. 1/4

Sample Bottle no.	Time	e/m	Height	Pressure	Remarks			
no.	no.							
1	4/12		100'	1310	131145	131230	10/8	ON DESCENT Purged from 300'
2	4/5		500'	1314	131727	131340	131800	1004
3	4/10		1000'	131920	132020	132130	081	
4	093		3000'	132330	132502	132536	015	
5	012		7000'	132700	132833	133310	285	START ALL AT BEGINNING OF RUN
6	088		150'	133800	134245	134445	573	AS5
7	4/6		200'	134730	135342	135625	467	AT START 5.6 BAR
8	4/11		FL	140250	140720	141010	/	1 run into run 5.6 BAR
9	4/3		FL	141215	141925	142007	—	ON DESCENT FROM FL30 ALL 1 run into run
10	4/2		3000'	142200	142737	142834	015	1 run purged on
11	5/1		1000'	143000	143535	143550	091	3 run purged on run
12	4/4		500'	143730	143820	143906		1 run purged on run

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A575 Date: 14/9/97 User: H. RICHEN
Interactive by: I. RUX
Date: 29/9/97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING USED

TWC

Profile plotted: YES P11
Line chosen: Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = - 0.1496E+1
b = + 0.5419E-2
c = + 0.3117E-6

LWC

NOT STORED

Heimann / Barnes

NOT USED

A575, 14th September, 1997
 ACSOE
 North Atlantic near the Azores

Start time	End time	Event	Height(s)	Hdg	Comments
123633					Take off St Maria
124855	130551	R1	FL060 FL080	180°	
131128	135336	P1	50' FL200	170°	Bottle fills at 100', 500', 1000', 3000', FL70 FL150, FL200
135336	140106	R2	FL200	185°	
140106	144016	P2	FL200 50'	185°	Bottle fills at 100', 500', 1000', 3000', FL70 FL150, FL200
144016	152159	P3	50' FL200	290°	Bottle fills at 100', 500', 1000', 3000', FL70 FL150, FL200
152159	152949	R3	FL200	280°	
152949	155514	P4	FL200 FL100	290°	
160110	162751	P5	FL100 FL220	275°	
162751	163301	R5	FL220	280°	
163301	171924	P6	FL220 50'	270°	Bottle fills at FL180 FL150, FL130, FL100, FL50 500'
171924	180736	P7	50' FL220	065°	Bottle fills at 100', FL50, FL100, FL130, FL150 FL180
180736	181325	R6	FL220	065°	
182814	191223	P8	50' FL220	080°	Bottle fills at 500', FL50, FL100, FL130, FL150 FL180, FL220
191623	192019	P9	FL220 FL180	080°	
192019	193553	R7	FL180	075°	
193553	194004	P10	FL180 FL220	080°	
194004	195948	P11	FL220 50'	040°	
200226	200701	R8	5000'	050°	
202810					Land St Maria

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 575

DATE: 14 19 197

Take off : 1235

Landing : 2030

Aircraft Scientist : H. RICHER
Flight Leader : I. RUIE
Others CO : S. SCHMITZ
ECKE : J. KENT
PSAP CNE : K. DEWET
BOTTLES : D. MERTON
PENEA : T. GILLEN
FOWLERHEAD : G. MILLS
PINCORDE : B. GANDY
NORRY : S. BARWITTE

Captain : M. PULSE
Co-pilot : D. BENDALL
Navigator : J. AYERS
Engineer : M. LEANARDS
Loadmaster : K. QUICK

+ PAUL LONKS
CLARE KEARNS
GRUBBY PENNETT
KATHY LAW } MISSION SCIENTISTS

Trials Instructions : MRF1 : ACCEX
Operating area : N. ATLANTIC

General synoptic situation

TIME :

Debrief

A successful science sortie was flown on the first day of the detachment from Santa Maria. The main aims of the experiment were met *i.e.* both tropical air and air with its origin over N. America were seemingly identified by their chemical signatures. All instruments were working although the PAN GC had excessive electrical noise for the first half of the flight and the NO_x background was found to vary. The CO sensitivity was also found to increase during the flight.

On leaving Santa Maria O_3 and CO values were low *e.g.* 55 ppb CO, 33 ppb O_3 at FL 100. However, these values were found to increase to *ca.* 70 ppb CO at FL160 and 65 ppb O_3 .

Throughout the flight observations of cumulus and stratocumulus clouds were made. However, the most notable feature was the poor visibility due to a thick haze layer as we flew south. This very humid air was rich in peroxide with readings of *ca.* 1.25 ppb. This haze became less notable as we ascended to the west. At the same time O_3 , CO and NO_y were found to increase. Maximum values of CO (*ca.* 120 ppb), O_3 (*ca.* 100 ppb) and NO_y (*ca.* 2 ppb) were found at altitude on the western leg of the sortie.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: HANNAH R RICHER

Project: ACSOE

Flight No: AS75

Date: 14/9/97

Page 1 of 8

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1240		Pres Rad FL			TAKE OFF SANTA MARIA + CLIMB TO 3000 feet
1243		3000 Pres Rad FL	168	36.56 -25.04	RAIN 3000ft for wet chem O3 18 ppb CO 88
1246		Pres Rad FL			REQUEST ASCENT TO FLOBO IN CLOUD
1248.55	RUN 1	060 Pres Rad FL	172 167	36.31 -24.96	NOxy CAR IN BETWEEN CLOUD
1250.5		Pres Rad FL			CLOUD SO HAVE TO CLIMB TO FLOBO
1251.51		080 Pres Rad FL	170		STILL MUCH MIXED LEVEL CLOUD HAVE TO DEVIATE FROM COURSE TO AVOID CLOUD
		Pres Rad FL			SMALL CU DEW AND STRATUS + STRATUS STRATOCU CIRRUS 1/8 above
1254.4		080 Pres Rad FL			STRATOCU NOW 8/8
13:01.28		080 Pres Rad FL	357	35.82 -24.82	TURN TO COMPLETE NOxy RUN IN CLEAR AIR
13:05.51		Pres Rad FL	160		DESCENT TO 50 feet 550mb inversion / cloud TYPICAL - MOST AIR
13:09.39		Pres Rad FL	160		PRIZZLE

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: HANNAH RICHOR

Project: AC50E
Flight No: A575

Date: 14/9/97
Page 2 of 8

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131241	P1	600ft Pres Rad FL		35.55 -24.6	bottle filled
131329	"	500ft Pres Rad FL	160	35.50 -24.66	bottle run
131813	"	500ft Pres Rad FL		35.27 -24.62	RESTART PROFILE
131905	"	010 Pres Rad FL	156	35.25 -24.61	bottle run
132138		Pres Rad FL	170	35.15 -24.58	restart profile THROUGH SMALL CU
132454	"	500ft Pres Rad FL	174	35.08 -24.53	IN CLOUD BOTTLE RUN
132539	"	Pres Rad FL		34.95 -24.52	RESTART PROFILE ABOVE CLOUD AT 5000 ft
133113	"	500ft Pres Rad FL	176	34.66 -24.46	1 MIN FOR NOXY ZERO
133316		Pres Rad FL	174	34.58 -24.45	RESTART PROFILE - JUST SMALL AMOUNT OF CIRROS ABOVE (1/4) 8/8 STRATOS BELOW.
		Pres Rad FL		34.41 -24.44	RATE OF CLIMB REDUCED TO
		FL100 Pres Rad FL			VERY LOW CO ~ 55 ppb O3 33 ppb INCREASE IN O3 65 ppb 10-12,000 ft

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: HANNAH RICHER

Project: ACSOE

Flight No: A575

Date: 14/9/97

Page 3 of 4

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	P1	Pres Rad FL			AND ALSO 14,000 feet
1342.62	P1	150 Pres Rad FL	183	33.94 -24.40	BOTTLE RUN at (ACCOMPLISHED ABOVE CO MAX) ~ 60 → 65 ppb
1346		160 Pres Rad FL		33.96 -24.44	Ozone increases density profile 66 ppb
1352	R2	200 Pres Rad FL		33.37 -24.40	CO up to 70 ppb End profile / Start run
		Profile 150 Pres Rad FL		32	1 minute zero for NO ₂ at beginning of every run
1405.55		150 Pres Rad FL		32.50 -24.31	Bottle filling run. (NO ₂ zero)
1410.7	P2	Pres Rad FL	174	32.21 -24.25	Restart P2 STRAINS show 8/8 H ₂ O up to 1.25 ppb
1418.12		070 Pres Rad FL		31.76 -24.16	BOTTLE RUN
1420.18		Pres Rad FL		31.62 -24.12	Restart profile
1428.23		200ft Pres Rad FL		31.55 -24.10	Bottle run
		1000ft Pres Rad FL			Bottle / cal run

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: HANNAH RICHER

Project: FCSOE

Flight No: AS75

Date: 14/9/97

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		500 Pres Rad FL			Bottle
	23	100 Pres Rad FL			} Heavy lurch.
		1000 Pres Rad FL			
		3000 Pres Rad FL			
15224		4200 Pres Rad FL	276	31.15 -25.81	Restart profile coming out of haze at ca. FL100
		7000 Pres Rad FL			Bottle fell
151120		150 Pres Rad FL			Bottle fell
1		2000 Pres Rad FL			
152159					Should now have 66 minutes to do a shallow sawtooth.
1					Cumulus(?) cloud streaks below haze Some cirrus and the odd large cum visible
153154		200 Pres Rad FL	272	31.20 -27.8	(corrective climb to starboard port side) Haze becoming more clear to starboard

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: R. CAER

Project: ACSOE - ON COA Date: 4/1/77
 Flight No: A575 Page 5 of 8

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				Longitude	
					Bath is dated
					as line of convective cloud visible - stratus behind
					On descent (slow smooth) go back into
					large large
					Shallow descent 400 feet/min
					More decreasing(?)
155514	P	00	274	31.45 -30.3	CALIBRATION / 2020 ft
160110	P5		258	31.4 -30.7	Resume profile at 400 feet/min back to FL 220
160824		013	263	31.41 -31.3	Here less notable but more cloud! layers of broken stratus below
161313		015	263	31.38 -31.82	CO, O ₃ , NO _y increasing on ascent from FL 100
1633		220		31.23 -33.51	O ₃ max ~ 90 ppb at FL 220.
163330	P6			31.21 -33.85	Profile descent @ 1000 ft/min. avoiding Cu cloud
163731		180		31.20 -33.89	Bath filling level
164155	P6			31.17 -34.17	Restart P6

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist:

Project: AC 58X Date: 11/09/97
 Flight No: A575 Page 6 of 8

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rel	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.	
						Latitude	Longitude			
164509			FL150		258	31.14		sharp dec. in NOY (0.35) to NOY, CO as (60) CO (9.3)		
1647			FL150		282	-34.34			Bright charge in heady to outside Cu clouds	
164843		P6	-			21.16				restart profile O3 & NOY remaining lower.
165057			FL130		245	31.20		bottle fluids run		
			FL100			-34.27				
165920		P6			250	31.16		restart profile		
						-35.28				
170515			FL050			31.07		recommends profile		
						-35.61				
170253		P6	FL050		249	31.04				
171604			SOFT		274	30.94		bottle fill		
						-36.12				
171810					099	30.99		recommends profile to 500 ft		
						-36.04				
171904		P7			92	30.99				
						-35.96		START P7.		
						30.99				
171944			100ft			-35.94				

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: RICHER

Project: AC50E Date: 4-19-1977
 Flight No: A575 Page 7 of 8

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rel	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
172031		P7			73	31.50	-35.57	Restart profile O ₃ & NO ₂ 0.3	
172935			FL050		50	31.33	-35.38	NOx ₂ zero & better R ₂	
173145		P7	FL100		49	31.40	-35.27	recurrence profile. O ₃ increasing to 7 ppb NO ₂ inc (0.3 ppb) NO _x 1, CO, pers. dia 2500' & better, h ₂ l recurrence profile	
174150		P7	FL130		52	31.51	-34.63	BATLE RLL	
174526						32.05	-34.36	recurrence - profile	
174847		P7	FL150			32.18	-34.13	BATLE	
175051			FL150			32.26	-34.05	O ₃ clearest straining steps up O ₃ with	
175419			FL180			32.63		Restart profile very large NO ₂ & O ₃ inc. O ₃ 2.5 → 150 ppb also NO ₂ double O ₃ & NO ₂ back to normal. O ₃ & NO ₂ increasing on level run, comax = 120	
1757			FL180			-33.48		recurrence - profile	
180114		P7						start run	
1802			FL220		248	33.16	-32.84	start run	

1822.39 6300ft

STARTED DESK (150 feet only).

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: RICHOR

Project: ACSOE
Flight No: AS75

Date: 4/9/97
Page 8 of 8

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude ----- Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
183255	Restart PR	Pres Red FL			
1839	F	250 Pres Red FL			Bottle fill
1841		100 Pres Red FL			CO & peroxide cal, bottle fill
184953	restart PR	Pres Red FL			O ₃ inc, CO inc (100ppb), NO _y (0.45)
185412		130 Pres Red FL			bottle fill
185710	restart PR	Pres Red FL			
		220 Pres Red FL			Bottle fill + cal
19419	R7	180 Pres Red FL			NO _y cal
19553	P10	Pres Red FL			
194004	P4	220 Pres Red FL			descent
195948	end P11	Pres Red FL			
200226	RP	Pres Red FL			JO'D RUN

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 575.....

Date 14/1/97.....

Page 1..... of 2.....

Video Tape	
No.	A575 #1
Ends	1541
<u>(FFC) / DFC / RFC</u>	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36° 58.38N	36 58.36N
Long	25° 09.46W	25 09.48W
Time	1019	1020
Status	53	GL AUGN

DRS recording to HORACE	<u>(y)</u> /n
HORACE recording to disc	<u>(y)</u> /n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	<u>(y)</u> /n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
104034				DATA ON					
121200				SET INU TO NAV					
123633				T/O ST MARIA					
124128	8			START VIDEO A575 #1		CANT = 0000			
124555	9	FL00		START	180	185	12	10	OFF
				END	RUN 1				
130551	11	FL080		180					
				START P1 ↑					
131128	12	50'	1020	170	182			OFF	SS=5
131140	13	100'		INTERUPT P1 - BOTTLE FILL					
131241	15	100'		RESUMPT P1					
131329	16	500		INTERUPT P1 - BOTTLE FILL					
131811	17	500'		RESUMPT P1					
131905	18	1000'		INTERUPT P1 - BOTTLE FILL					
132138	19	1050'		RESUMPT P1					
132454	20	3000'		ENDUPT P1		BOTTLE FILL			
132539	21	3000'		RESUMPT P1					
133113	23	FL070		INTERUPT P1		-BOTTLE FILL / NOXY ZERO			
133316	24	FL070		RESUMPT P1					
134202	26	FL150		INTERUPT P1		BOTTLE FILL			
134468	27	FL150		RESUMPT P1					
		FL150		END	RESUMPT P1		BOTTLE FILL / START RUN 2		
135336	29	FL200		190	160			OFF	

Video Tape	
No.	A575 #1
Ends	1541 / 1740
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	33 09.33N	32 45.26
Long	24 24.65 W	24 21.40 W
Time	1358	1402
Status	S's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
			END RUN 2			START P2			
140106	30	FL200		185	205	-11	-30	OFF	
140555	31	FL150	INTERUPT P2					BOTTLE FULL	
141017	32	FL150	RESTART P2						
141812	33	FL070	INTERUPT P2					BOTTLE FULL	
142018	34	FL070	RESTART P2						500/min (2) 500'
142623	36	3200'	(100) INTERUPT P2					BOTTLE FULL	
142840	37	3200'	RESTART P2						
143239	38	1020'	INTERUPT P2					BOTTLE FULL	
143600	40	1000'	RESTART P2						
143656	42	500'	INTERUPT P2					BOTTLE FULL	
143912	43	500	RESTART P2						
144016	44	500'	END INTERUPT P2					BOTTLE FULL / START P3	(105) 29'
144024	45	100'	(103) INTERUPT P3					BOTTLE FULL	SS=2
144134	46	100'	RESTART P3						
144217	47	500'	INTERUPT P3					BOTTLE FULL	
144402	48	500'	1023	290	RESTART P3				
144436	49	1020'	1023	285	INTERUPT P3			BOTTLE FULL	
144648	51	1020'	1023	285	RESTART P3				
145031	52	3200'		285	INTERUPT P3				
145400	53	3200'		285	RESTART P3				1000/min (2) 6000'
150011	55	FL070	1013		INTERUPT P3			BOTTLE FULL	
150224	56	FL070		290	RESTART P3				
151120	57	FL150		290	INTERUPT P3			BOTTLE FULL	
151431	58	FL150		290	RESTART P3				
152154	59	FL200		(20) END	INTERUPT P3			START RUN 3	
152449	60	FL200		250	END RUN 3			START P4	400/min
154001	61				STOP UNDER A575 #1			COUNT = 6045	
154046	62				START VIDEO A575 #2			COUNT = 0200	
155514	63	FL100	1013	290	END P4			START RUN 4	
160110	64	FL100		275	END RUN 4			START P5	400/min
162751	65	FL220			END P5			START RUN 5	

et Research Flight

ETA 2000

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 575.....

Date 14/9/97.....

Page 2 of 2.....

Video Tape	
No.	<u>A575#2</u>
Ends	<u>1740</u>
<u>(FFC) / DFC / RFC</u>	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	<u>(y)</u> n
HORACE recording to disc	<u>(y)</u> n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	<u>(y)</u> n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END RUN 5 / START P6 ↓						
163301	66	FL220		280				OFF	FL180
165731	67	FL180		270	INTERLOFT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
164155	68	FL180		270	RESTANT P6			OFF	
164504	69	FL150		270	INTERLOFT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
164843	70	FL150		280	RESTANT P6				
165057	71	FL130		280	INTERLOFT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
165353	72	FL130		280	RESTANT P6				
165655	73	FL100		265	INTERLOFT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
165910	74	FL100		265	RESTANT P6				
170231	75	5200'		265	INTERLOFT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
170757	76	5000'			RESTANT P6				
171604	77	500'			INTERLOFT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
171810	78	500'		110	RESTANT P6				
172224	79	50'	1015	115	END P6 / START P7				SS=6
171944	80	100'			INTERLOFT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
172037	81	100'		065	RESTANT P7				
172935	82	5000'		060	INTERLOFT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
173135	83	5000'		065	RESTANT P7				
173635	84	FL100		065	INTERLOFT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
174150	85	FL100		065	RESTANT P7				
174526	86	FL130		060	INTERLOFT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
174847	87	FL130		065	RESTANT P7				
175051	88	FL150		065	INTERLOFT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
175419	89	FL150		065	RESTANT P7				
175742	90	FL170		065	INTERLOFT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
180114	91	FL180		065	RESTANT P7				
180736	92	FL220		END	RESTANT P7 // START RUN 6				
181328	93	FL220		END	RUN 6				

Video Tape

No. A575

Ends 1840 / 2138

(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE (y/n)

HORACE recording to disc (y/n)

SATCOM sending pos reports y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
18284	94	50'	1013	080	START PT				SS=7
18289	95	500'		085	INTERUPT PT			BOTTLE FILL	
18325	96	500'			RESUMPT PT				
18391	99	5000'			INTERUPT PT			BOTTLE FILL	
18372	97		STOP	VIDEO	A575 #2	COUNT = 0053			
18385	98		START	VIDEO	A575 #3	COUNT = 0000			
18417	100	5000'		080	RESUMPT PT				
18419	101	FL00		080	INTERUPT PT			BOTTLE FILL	
18453	102	FL00		080	RESUMPT PT				
18534	103	FL30			INTERUPT PT			BOTTLE FILL	
18570	104	FL30		080	RESUMPT PT				
18914	105	FL50		080	INTERUPT PT			BOTTLE FILL	
19023	106	FL50		080	RESUMPT PT				
19055	107	FL80		080	INTERUPT PT			BOTTLE FILL	
19086	108	FL80		080	RESUMPT PT				
19123	109	FL20		080	END PT			BOTTLE FILL	
19163	110	FL20		080	START P9				
19209	111	FL80		080	END P9 / START CAL	P10N			P7
19353	112	FL80		075	END R7 / START	P10 P11			
19404	113	FL20		080	END P10 / START	P11			
19914	114	50'	1017	040	END P11				SS=3/4
20026	115	5000'	1010	050	START RUN 8				
20070	116	5000'		050	END RUN 8				
20174	117				VIDEO A575 #3	52003			COUNT = 4053
201810				LAND	ST INHALA				
				DATA	OFF			GPS POS	
								30 58.36 N	
								25 01.46 W	

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A575

Date: 14/9/17

Page...1..of 2

CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2853	✓		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	4045	✓ (F/S) O/S	TORQUE 4.0	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	4045	✓ (F/S) O/S	TORQUE 3.5	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000	✓		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3886	200 ✓		As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3317	1005 ✓			
	A/S	9	0578	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	0871		TOID		
	UP2S	82	0682		NED		
	UIRS	83	0336		JNO2		
	UP1Z	84	0878		TOID	Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	0146	✓	NED	Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	0336		JNO2	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	0987		TOID	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2344	20 ✓	NED	As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000		JNO2	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0114		TOID		
	LP2S	92	0146		NED		
	LIRS	93	0071		JNO2		
	LP1Z	94	0110		TOID	Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	0157	✓	NED	Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0071		JNO2	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	0000		TOID	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2338	20 ✓	NED	As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000		JNO2	As IAT	
	J/W	42	0100	0 ✓		As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	3085	20 ✓			
	HYCC	59	0712			696-901	
	FDEW	138	2499	10 ?		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	0008				
	DTP	10	1450	23			
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	1687	23		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	0				
	INCT	48	2725	✓			
	HEIM	141	2638				
	PRTC	142	2382	✓		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	1027	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	0213	✓		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0089	✓			
	O3P	106	2048			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	2027				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	525			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0111	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0338	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	7			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3775	1492	3777	0478	3772	3682	3772	0137
	3856						
	LATC	160	Dec	0220			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0700			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 0'

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	6007	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1255	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0216	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2577	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	1256	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2088	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2120	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	104	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	6082	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2023				
	EV2V	171	2023				
	NPWR	172	333A				
	EVIC	173	3468				
	EV2C	174	3468				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear J210	☐ Off ☐ On	Large ☐ Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon J212		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear J010	☐ Off ☐ On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon J212		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Page 2 of 2

Flight No: 875 Date: 14/9/97

CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES
	REF +	5	0567	✓		Approx 068
	REF -	7	2855	✓		Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	1871		TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1021		TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	1005	✓	8000	As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2007	✓		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	2483	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	A/S	9	1244	✓		
	UPIS	81	4048		JDID	
	UP2S	82	1971		RD	
	URS	83	1039		JDID	
	UP1Z	84	4025		JDID	Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0000	✓	RD	Approx 0149
	URZ	86	1000		JDID	Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	4045		JDID	As IAT
	UP2T	88	2058		RD	As IAT
	UR1T	89	0001		JDID	As IAT
	LP1S	91	2344		JDID	
	LP2S	92	0261		RD	
	LRBS	93	2080		JDID	
	LP1Z	94	0074		JDID	Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0051	✓	RD	Approx 0146
	LRZ	96	2177		JDID	Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	1526		JDID	As IAT
	LP2T	98	0007	✓	RD	As IAT
	LR1T	99	1455		JDID	As IAT
	J/W	42	1213	0.1		As Indicated 0000
	HYGR	58	3108	HI		
	HYCC	59	0716	✓		696-901
	EDW	138	0114	6	CEL	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	PSTA	139	0002			
	DTE	10	1308	21		
	DTC	11	0			
	NDTF	23	1073	20		same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	0			
	INCT	48	2457			
	HEIM	141	2855	✓		
	PRIC	142	0382	✓		approx 2380
	TWCD	70	1989			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	1185			0640-1860 > min
	O3	100	0057			
	O3P	106	1583			
	O3RG	113	2247			
						$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$

IGC SAMPLE RECORD

Clouds:
1
2
3

MAIN
39.
39.
39.

B/FLUSH. up/down
37.5
44
39.4

GC run in

Flight no. A575
Date 14/9/97

56
1

IC	Time	Height	Ch. 1			Ch. 2			Ch. 3			Notes	
			ST	SP	P.C	ST	SP	P.C	ST	SP	P.C		
1		GROUND											
1	13356	FL200	453	1184		488	1601		461	1554			
2	14036	FL500	453	1291		489	1726		461	1678		As found in mid-air	
3	14414	500'	451	1723		488	2252		460	2186		Sim PAN	
4	14527	300'	451	1606		488	2092		461	2052		PAN	
5	15024	700'	452	1428		488	1844		461	1794			
6	151140	FL150	454	261		489	1665		462	1612			
7	15221	FL200	457	1154		491	1516		464	1465			
		16000'	Reopened				2=9						
8	174601	FL80	447	1402		483	1787		456	1839			
9	17553	FL170	449	1300		484	1643		457	1595			
10	180440	FL210	451	1198		485	1448		458	1494			
11	182891	500'	450	1742		486	2106		457	2107			
12	18514	FL2060	449	1502		485	1496		454	1887			

DATE 14 SEP 97	FTI No 01	FLT No AS75	NAV AMELI
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD SANTA MARIA		ATIS R/W 18 150/17 CAVOK 23/20 H 1020	
ATC CLEARANCE FPR			TAKE OFF TIME 1236

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1248 ⁵⁵	168	4P	193	180	202	230/23	F060	1020	3623.7	02459.8	R1
1305 ⁵¹							F080	1020	3555.0	02451.2	ER1
1311 ²⁸							50'↑				P1.4
1312 ⁴¹							100'↑				RP1.4
1313 ¹⁹							500'		3531.7	02441.0	1P1
1318 ¹¹							1000'		3519.1	02438.5	R01
1324 ⁵⁹							3000'		3501.3	02432.0	1P1
1331 ¹³							F070		3442.0	02427.9	1P1
1342 ⁴²							F150		3402.6	02424.2	1P1
1353 ³⁴							F200		3322.7	02424.4	EP1/R2
1401 ⁰⁶							F200		3249.9	02422.5	ER2/P2
1405 ⁵⁹							F150		3230.6	02418.8	1P2
1418 ¹²							F070		3145.8	02409.3	1P2
1426 ²³							3000'	1020	3118.8	02403.4	1P2
1432 ³⁹	275	3S	185	178	184	223/03	1000'		3059.6	02400.1	1P2
1436 ⁵⁶							500'		3059.3	02414.1	1P2
1440 ¹⁶							50'↑ EP1/S		3100.3	02426.3	EP2/S
1440 ²⁹											1P3
1442 ¹⁷							500'		3100.6	02433.2	1P3
1444 ³⁶							1000'		3101.5	02441.4	1P3
1450 ³¹							3000'		3103.6	02501.9	1P3
1500 ¹¹							F070		3107.5	02535.4	1P3
1511 ²⁰							F150		3112.7	02618.6	1P3
1521 ⁵⁹							F200		3117.3	02705.9	EP3/R3
1529 ⁴⁹							F200		3117.6	02743.0	ER3/P4

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	TAKE OFF
ATIS	FLIGHT TIME

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD		ATIS	
ATC CLEARANCE			TAKE OFF TIME 1236

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1555 ¹⁴	273	33	296	266	319	245/25	F100	1020	3127.1	03015.1	EP4/R4
1601 ¹⁰									3127.9	03047.4	EP4/P5
1627 ⁵¹							F220		3117.3	03301.7	EP5/R5
1633 ⁰¹									3114.5	03328.1	EP5/P6
1637 ³¹							F180		3113.3	03352.2	IP6
1645 ⁰⁹							F150		3108.7	03423.8	IP6
1650 ⁵⁹						248/30	F130		3112.1	03446.4	IP6
1656 ⁵⁵							F100		3112.9	03508.9	IP6
1704 ³¹							F050		3106.4	03532.6	IP6
1716 ⁰⁴							500'		3056.6	03607.1	IP6
1719 ²⁴							50'		3059.3	03600.3	EP6/P7
1719 ⁴⁴	049	13	215	176	186	235/30	100'		3059.3	03559.0	IP7
1729 ⁵⁵							F050		3119.3	03524.0	IP7
1736 ³⁵							F100		3136.8	03456.9	IP7
1745 ²⁶							F130		3200.7	03422.7	IP7
1748 ⁵¹							F150		3215.7	03400.9	IP7
1757 ⁴⁷							F180		3235.6	03332.5	IP7
1807 ⁵⁶							F220		3304.2	03248.2	EP7/R6
1813 ²⁵							F220		3306.0	03302.8	EP6
1818 ¹⁴							50'		3259.6	03301.7	IP8
1828 ⁵⁹	068	48	209	176	184	211/33	500'		3300.8	03259.0	IP8
1839 ¹⁵							F050		3318.9	03218.3	IP8
1846 ²⁹							F100		3332.3	03146.0	IP8
1853 ⁴⁴							F135				IP8
1857 ¹⁰							F130		3347.6	03109.7	IP8

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	TAKE OFF
ATIS	FLIGHT TIME

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A575

DATE: 14 ' 9 ' 97

MRF / Aesø

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	✓	✓	
HEIMANN	✓	✓	
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	✓	✓	
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	TOLD ✓	✓	
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	INO₂ ✓	✓	
LOWER CLEAR	TOLD ✓	✓	
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	INO₂ ✓	✓	
MARSS	X		
SAFIRE	X		
DEIMOS	X		
ARIES	X		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	X	X	
CLOUD PHYSICS	X	X	
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	X		
PSAP	✓	✓	

A575 14-SEP-97 Data starts 09:03:31 Data ends 20:31:47

Header file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A575_RAW_HDDR.DAT;
Data file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A575_RAW_DATA.DAT; 78.8 Mbytes (161320 blocks)

Transcription on 26-SEP-97 11:51:32
Extraction on 26-SEP-97 11:51:32

Data set type 2

ISS 31 DBF 31 IC 02 121 parameters recorded 889 samples per second

14 sections of data

Section	Starts					Ends				
	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC
1	09:03:31	032611	000	00010	00001	09:48:30	035310	006	02709	02700
2	09:58:53	035933	006	03332	02701	11:31:52	041512	007	08911	08280
3	11:37:00	041820	007	09219	08281	13:08:40	047320	011	14719	13781
4	13:08:44	047324	011	14723	13782	17:42:51	063771	085	31170	30229
5	17:42:55	063775	085	31174	30230	17:45:01	063901	085	31300	30356
6	17:45:05	063905	085	31304	30357	17:45:07	063907	085	31306	30359
7	17:45:11	063911	085	31310	30360	17:57:08	064628	089	32027	31077
8	17:57:12	064632	089	32031	31078	18:15:34	065734	093	33133	32180
9	18:15:38	065738	093	33137	32181	18:39:27	067167	099	34566	33610
10	18:39:31	067171	099	34570	33611	18:39:57	067197	099	34596	33637
11	18:40:01	067201	099	34600	33638	20:07:56	072476	116	39875	38913
12	20:07:58	072478	116	39877	38914	20:07:58	072478	116	39877	38914
13	20:08:00	072480	116	39879	38915	20:27:59	073679	117	41078	40114
14	20:28:12	073692	117	41091	40115	20:31:47	073907	117	41306	40330

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
✓	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEMOS log Chemistry log <i>bottles, ECG</i>
✓	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
✓ ✓ ✓	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 15 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Stereocord Pencil 60°N, Original scale 1:1000000

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 33

14 SEP 197 04:45

MET OFFICE TOTAL PAGE 001 **

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 14 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:200,000

MET OFFICE TOTAL PAGE.001 **

Prepared and drawn in the Cartographic Service, MET OFFICE, 51900000 MET OFFICE TOTAL PAGE.001 **

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE T:20H RUN TIME 03.44.10

CHART 27

PHD50 EGRR 0000Z

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_1 PAGE.001

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-4 PAGE.001

14 SEP . 97 04:00

300MB

HEIGHT DM.

GMAIN T + 24

15/ 9/97

VI UUZ MUN

NEAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.43.30

CHART 27

PHDE30 EGRR 00007

01 00Z SUN 14/ 9/97 VI 00Z SUN 14/ 9/97 GMAIN T+ 0

HEIGHT DM. 300MB

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-6 PAGE.001

14 SEP . 97 03:48

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.34.45

CHART 27

[PH0A30 ECCR 00007]

14 SEP 97 03:24

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

.03 .1 .5 1.0

MM/HR AT VI

DT 00Z SUNDAY 14/9/1997 LMAIN

I+12 VI 12Z SUNDAY 14/9/1997

14 SEP . 97 03:31

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z SUNDAY 14/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC
MM/HR AT VT
.05 .1 .5 1.0

STATION: 08509
 LAJES (ACORES)
 TIME: 140000 +12 SEP 97

mb	Deg	Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL		
150	285	21
201	300	37
251	280	35
302	260	18
358	250	23
427	245	24
511	235	22
608	230	22
710	215	22
804	205	25
883	190	28
945	170	32
990	155	30
1013	155	23

Parts : A C D missing

STATION: 08509
 LAJES (ACORES)
 TIME: 140000 +24 SEP 97

mb	Deg	Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL		
150	275	25
200	265	9
251	240	20
301	240	20
357	235	20
425	235	23
509	235	23
606	235	24
707	245	21
801	255	19
880	250	19
941	245	21
986	230	21
1008	215	14

Parts : A C D missing

Figure 1(a) Back Trajectories

From 12Z 10/ 9/1997 to 18Z 14/ 9/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A575 14-SEP-97

P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles)(131128-135336) + P2 FL200-50' (+bottles)(140106-144016)

A575 14-SEP-97

P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles)(144016-152159) + P4 FL200-FL100(152949-155514)

A575 14-SEP-97

P5 FL100-FL220(160110-162751) + P6 FL220-50'(163301-171924)

A575 14-SEP-97

P7 50'-FL220(171924-180736) + Descent(181325-182814)

A575 14-SEP-97

P8 50'-FL220(182814-191223) + P9 FL220-FL180(191623-192019)

A575 14-SEP-97

P10 FL180-FL220(193553-194004) + P11 FL220-50'(194004-195948)

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1017
Mean 765.704
Standard dev 24.0289
Max value 814.782
Min value 751.255

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1017
Mean 283.617
Standard dev 0.933757
Max value 285.853
Min value 282.587

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1017
Mean 281.007
Standard dev 1.82045
Max value 285.116
Min value 277.010

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1017
Mean 26.1333
Standard dev 2.57327
Max value 35.4262
Min value 18.3746

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 1017
Mean 7.234207e-08
Standard dev 4.219167e-07
Max value 3.784467e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 1017
Mean 37.3718
Standard dev 4.60501
Max value 57.2378
Min value 13.5881

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1017
Mean 2303.91
Standard dev 246.764
Max value 2452.87
Min value 1801.06

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1017
Mean 36.0368
Standard dev 0.170954
Max value 36.3937
Min value 35.7957

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1017
Mean -24.8778
Standard dev 6.138094e-02
Max value -24.7766
Min value -24.9970

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1017
Mean 7.42022
Standard dev 1.81213
Max value 10.7293
Min value 2.18573

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1017
Mean 7.34786
Standard dev 1.93513
Max value 11.7024
Min value 2.78451

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1017
Mean -0.170764
Standard dev 0.547663
Max value 1.67651
Min value -1.53003

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1017
Mean 10.5489
Standard dev 2.19053
Max value 14.4410
Min value 4.26526

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 224.719

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1017
Mean 105.505
Standard dev 2.54753
Max value 110.330
Min value 100.757

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 166.298

A575 14-SEP-97 R1 FL060-FL080

From 124855-130551 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:02

A575 14-SEP-97 R1 FL060-FL080 From 124855-130551 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:02

A575 14-SEP-97 R1 FL060-FL080 From 124855~130551 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:02

A575 14-SEP-97 R1 FL060-FL080 From 124855-130551 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:02

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:17

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 2529
Mean 766.019
Standard dev 189.931
Max value 1017.78
Min value 465.826

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 2529
Mean 282.671
Standard dev 11.1741
Max value 296.787
Min value 261.834

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 2529
Mean 274.488
Standard dev 19.1384
Max value 295.302
Min value 230.435

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 2529
Mean 33.8931
Standard dev 15.1782
Max value 66.7130
Min value 16.7281

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
No of obs 2529
Mean 1.502323e-06
Standard dev 2.553305e-06
Max value 1.283306e-05
Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
No of obs 2529
Mean 30.7301
Standard dev 15.2020
Max value 54.1442
Min value 2.77443

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 2529
Mean 2507.96
Standard dev 2056.56
Max value 6092.88
Min value -37.6557

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2529
Mean 34.5805
Standard dev 0.653325
Max value 35.6151
Min value 33.3763

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2529
Mean -24.4953
Standard dev 0.100939
Max value -24.4036
Min value -24.7367

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2529
Mean 5.69537
Standard dev 4.64089
Max value 14.1576
Min value -1.84420

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2529
Mean 5.91872
Standard dev 4.88311
Max value 13.9252
Min value -4.50828

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2529
Mean -0.794979
Standard dev 0.592465
Max value 1.70741
Min value -2.31192

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 2529
Mean 10.3567
Standard dev 2.36074
Max value 15.4391
Min value 5.70726

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 226.102

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 2529
Mean 105.009
Standard dev 8.32023
Max value 121.820
Min value 93.0027

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 173.107

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:17

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:17

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:17

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:17

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128 - 135336 Plotted 6--May-1998 16:17

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:16

A575 14-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 131128-135336 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:16

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 451
 Mean 465.423
 Standard dev 0.317595
 Max value 466.094
 Min value 464.845

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 451
 Mean 261.459
 Standard dev 0.189686
 Max value 261.834
 Min value 261.008

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 451
 Mean 231.797
 Standard dev 2.14404
 Max value 241.786
 Min value 230.082

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 451
 Mean 58.4854
 Standard dev 3.20486
 Max value 66.4328
 Min value 52.8678

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 451
 Mean 1.163554e-07
 Standard dev 3.439951e-07
 Max value 1.732963e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 451
 Mean 39.5361
 Standard dev 6.97258
 Max value 47.1502
 Min value 10.7509

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 451
 Mean 8099.17
 Standard dev 4.96348
 Max value 6108.22
 Min value 6088.70

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 451
 Mean 33.1114
 Standard dev 0.161510
 Max value 33.3763
 Min value 32.8312

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 451
 Mean -24.4044
 Standard dev 9.610767e-03
 Max value -24.3753
 Min value -24.4117

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 451
 Mean 1.45660
 Standard dev 0.280078
 Max value 2.05841
 Min value 0.913498

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 451
 Mean 7.10208
 Standard dev 0.435941
 Max value 8.09218
 Min value 6.07495

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 451
 Mean -0.454211
 Standard dev 0.263122
 Max value 5.134583e-02
 Min value -0.948013

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 451
 Mean 7.25638
 Standard dev 0.417618
 Max value 8.26646
 Min value 6.31185

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 258.410

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 451
 Mean 136.068
 Standard dev 9.74306
 Max value 148.141
 Min value 112.263

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 177.126

A575 14-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 135336-140106 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:21

A575 14-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 135336-140106 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:21

A575 14-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 135336-140106 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:21

A575 14-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 135336-140106 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:21

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:36

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2351
Mean 781.881
Standard dev 175.195
Max value 1018.98
Min value 466.078

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2351
Mean 284.699
Standard dev 10.7467
Max value 298.675
Min value 261.025

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2351
Mean 271.262
Standard dev 22.2967
Max value 296.105
Min value 232.837

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2351
Mean 34.5698
Standard dev 15.4873
Max value 71.6350
Min value 13.0509

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2351
Mean 4.303929e-06
Standard dev 3.879622e-06
Max value 1.913411e-05
Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 2351
Mean 26.5548
Standard dev 7.57209
Max value 37.2179
Min value 8.94103

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2351
Mean 2307.68
Standard dev 1879.87
Max value 6088.95
Min value -47.6172

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2351
Mean 31.6936
Standard dev 0.588806
Max value 32.8312
Min value 30.9702

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2351
Mean -24.1827
Standard dev 0.116516
Max value -24.0024
Min value -24.4387

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2351
Mean 2.73475
Standard dev 1.24560
Max value 5.27303
Min value -1.73598

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2351
Mean 7.01787
Standard dev 4.55094
Max value 16.3216
Min value -0.676323

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2351
Mean 0.155462
Standard dev 0.566068
Max value 1.71658
Min value -1.27860

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2351
Mean 7.98853
Standard dev 3.89515
Max value 16.4240
Min value 2.20931

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 248.710

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2351
Mean 107.617
Standard dev 10.8973
Max value 131.924
Min value 91.2417

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 181.826

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:36

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:35

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:35

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:35

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:35

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:35

A575 14-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 140106-144016 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:35

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:58

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'--FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:58

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:58

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:58

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:59

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:59

A575 14-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 144016-152159 Plotted 6-May-1998 16:59

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 765.479
 Standard dev 179.407
 Max value 1018.98
 Min value 463.758

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 283.414
 Standard dev 11.6811
 Max value 298.666
 Min value 261.409

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 276.801
 Standard dev 14.9029
 Max value 296.217
 Min value 230.773

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 34.6571
 Standard dev 12.5087
 Max value 65.6294
 Min value 18.0427

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 1.735284e-06
 Standard dev 2.431141e-06
 Max value 1.818163e-05
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 21.8861
 Standard dev 7.39660
 Max value 34.6801
 Min value 7.01193

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 2491.94
 Standard dev 1949.55
 Max value 6125.24
 Min value -47.6172

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 31.1377
 Standard dev 8.482475e-02
 Max value 31.2892
 Min value 31.0064

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean -25.6964
 Standard dev 0.759600
 Max value -24.4387
 Min value -27.1040

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 2.75806
 Standard dev 1.60733
 Max value 5.78466
 Min value -1.35207

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 5.34083
 Standard dev 4.04902
 Max value 13.3180
 Min value -0.476448

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean -0.712872
 Standard dev 0.471409
 Max value 0.441719
 Min value -1.76247

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 6.29357
 Standard dev 3.93688
 Max value 14.1136
 Min value 0.177377

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 242.688

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 2504
 Mean 107.147
 Standard dev 10.0200
 Max value 124.557
 Min value 90.0028

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 277.029

A575 14-SEP-97 R3 FL200 From 152159-152949 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:01

A575 14-SEP-97 R3 FL200 From 152159-152949 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:01

A575 14-SEP-97 R3 FL200 From 152159-152949 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:01

A575 14-SEP-97 R3 FL200 From 152159-152949 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:01

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 464.587
 Standard dev 0.396605
 Max value 465.818
 Min value 463.717

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 261.385
 Standard dev 0.150721
 Max value 261.833
 Min value 261.122

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 238.533
 Standard dev 3.69193
 Max value 247.409
 Min value 231.134

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 63.0830
 Standard dev 2.68972
 Max value 69.6913
 Min value 53.8298

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
 No of obs 471
 Mean 9.927899e-07
 Standard dev 1.889613e-06
 Max value 8.791114e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 31.3110
 Standard dev 8.44799
 Max value 35.3995
 Min value 10.5342

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 6112.26
 Standard dev 6.20574
 Max value 6125.88
 Min value 6093.00

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 31.2985
 Standard dev 2.559636e-03
 Max value 31.3017
 Min value 31.2892

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 471
 Mean -27.4115
 Standard dev 0.179322
 Max value -27.1040
 Min value -27.7218

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 5.29777
 Standard dev 0.782840
 Max value 7.76388
 Min value 3.69560

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 4.72695
 Standard dev 0.437996
 Max value 5.56995
 Min value 3.85091

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 471
 Mean -0.663827
 Standard dev 0.320663
 Max value -7.775116e-02
 Min value -1.54126

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 7.12809
 Standard dev 0.636054
 Max value 9.28889
 Min value 5.82663

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 221.741

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 471
 Mean 129.982
 Standard dev 2.80016
 Max value 136.347
 Min value 118.594

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 270.620

A575 14-SEP-97 P4 FL200-FL100 From 152949-155514 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:09

A575 14--SEP--97 P4 FL200--FL100 From 152949--155514 Plotted 6--May--1998 17:09

A575 14-SEP-97 P4 FL200-FL100 From 152949-155514 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:09

A575 14-SEP-97 P5 FL100-FL220 From 160110-162751 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:16

A575 14-SEP-97 P5 FL100-FL220 From 160110-162751 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:16

A575 14-SEP-97 P5 FL100-FL220 From 160110-162751 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:16

A575 14-SEP-97 R5 FL220 From 162751-163301 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:18

A575 14-SEP-97 R5 FL220 From 162751-163301 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:18

A575 14-SEP-97 R5 FL220 From 162751-163301 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:18

A575 14-SEP-97 R5 FL220 From 162751-163301 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:18

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 428.936
 Standard dev 0.158554
 Max value 429.276
 Min value 428.522

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 256.910
 Standard dev 0.220795
 Max value 257.329
 Min value 256.534

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 233.679
 Standard dev 0.789614
 Max value 234.564
 Min value 232.404

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 85.4234
 Standard dev 4.76614
 Max value 96.7121
 Min value 79.4103

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
 No of obs 311
 Mean -1.046657e-09
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value -1.046657e-09
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 26.4674
 Standard dev 4.94489
 Max value 30.3455
 Min value 8.78930

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 6688.43
 Standard dev 2.64723
 Max value 6695.34
 Min value 6682.75

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 31.2664
 Standard dev 1.420988e-02
 Max value 31.2896
 Min value 31.2419

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 311
 Mean -33.2458
 Standard dev 0.127963
 Max value -33.0322
 Min value -33.4709

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 2.79038
 Standard dev 0.688792
 Max value 4.00636
 Min value 1.36107

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 12.9359
 Standard dev 0.306554
 Max value 13.5944
 Min value 12.1942

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 311
 Mean -0.629300
 Standard dev 0.413982
 Max value 0.125198
 Min value -1.28475

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 13.2517
 Standard dev 0.290485
 Max value 14.0824
 Min value 12.7144

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 257.827

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 311
 Mean 149.045
 Standard dev 6.55771
 Max value 156.903
 Min value 132.735

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 262.794

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:29

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:29

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:29

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:29

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:29

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:30

A575 14-SEP-97 P6 FL220-50' From 163301-171924 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:30

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 702.703
 Standard dev 176.340
 Max value 1012.01
 Min value 429.033

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 280.549
 Standard dev 11.6402
 Max value 300.151
 Min value 256.907

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 261.941
 Standard dev 23.6851
 Max value 295.607
 Min value 234.364

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 55.5919
 Standard dev 19.2590
 Max value 88.7353
 Min value 26.0789

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2784
 Mean 2.821758e-06
 Standard dev 6.649434e-06
 Max value 5.000437e-05
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 21.2435
 Standard dev 6.53291
 Max value 39.0742
 Min value 8.76763

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 3183.10
 Standard dev 1977.84
 Max value 6686.81
 Min value 10.3248

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 31.1302
 Standard dev 9.269220e-02
 Max value 31.2419
 Min value 30.9435

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2784
 Mean -35.0512
 Standard dev 1.90185
 Max value -33.4709
 Min value -126.527

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 6.71815
 Standard dev 4.97817
 Max value 248.502
 Min value 2.68371

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 14.7790
 Standard dev 24.7632
 Max value 24.6665
 Min value -1279.95

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 0.365628
 Standard dev 11.3725
 Max value 599.555
 Min value -1.69834

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2782
 Mean 16.7328
 Standard dev 3.27951
 Max value 26.4044
 Min value 11.4480

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 245.555

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2784
 Mean 115.319
 Standard dev 17.0992
 Max value 173.138
 Min value 92.6270

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 263.500

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

A575 14-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL220 From 171924-180736 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:38

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 683.140
 Standard dev 168.165
 Max value 1011.95
 Min value 429.268

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 279.809
 Standard dev 11.4332
 Max value 300.161
 Min value 257.625

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 258.112
 Standard dev 20.0497
 Max value 295.703
 Min value 236.990

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 62.9945
 Standard dev 18.2067
 Max value 102.807
 Min value 32.4807

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2881
 Mean 5.305006e-07
 Standard dev 1.441111e-06
 Max value 9.560426e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 12.3314
 Standard dev 1.82690
 Max value 14.4096
 Min value 7.32622

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 3392.89
 Standard dev 1909.68
 Max value 6682.88
 Min value 10.7982

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 31.9507
 Standard dev 0.623389
 Max value 33.0715
 Min value 30.9871

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2881
 Mean -34.4741
 Standard dev 0.923619
 Max value -32.8028
 Min value -36.0052

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 10.5128
 Standard dev 1.75330
 Max value 15.0913
 Min value 6.18201

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 16.1073
 Standard dev 3.04021
 Max value 25.2870
 Min value 7.88285

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2881
 Mean -0.574460
 Standard dev 0.454077
 Max value 0.768425
 Min value -1.65181

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 19.3565
 Standard dev 2.75741
 Max value 29.0352
 Min value 11.7391

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 236.869

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2881
 Mean 113.249
 Standard dev 10.9937
 Max value 132.822
 Min value 91.3908

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 52.6886

A575 14-SEP-97 R6 FL220 From 180736-181325 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:39

A575 14-SEP-97 R6 FL220 From 180736-181325 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:39

A575 14-SEP-97 R6 FL220 From 180736-181325 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:39

A575 14-SEP-97 R6 FL220 From 180736-181325 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:39

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 350
Mean 427.733
Standard dev 0.817909
Max value 429.268
Min value 425.870

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 350
Mean 257.249
Standard dev 0.210837
Max value 257.625
Min value 256.928

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 350
Mean 242.475
Standard dev 1.36869
Max value 244.453
Min value 238.324

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 350
Mean 73.6592
Standard dev 6.87998
Max value 86.5262
Min value 62.2113

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
No of obs 350
Mean 1.350923e-07
Standard dev 2.597779e-07
Max value 8.659579e-07
Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/5)
No of obs 350
Mean 12.6328
Standard dev 0.777069
Max value 13.6218
Min value 8.11737

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 350
Mean 6708.55
Standard dev 13.6855
Max value 6739.78
Min value 6682.88

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 350
Mean 33.1408
Standard dev 3.164698e-02
Max value 33.1872
Min value 33.0715

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 350
Mean -32.8603
Standard dev 9.621365e-02
Max value -32.7432
Min value -33.0480

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 350
Mean 7.29926
Standard dev 0.797598
Max value 9.36088
Min value 6.20987

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 350
Mean 15.1712
Standard dev 0.459562
Max value 15.8148
Min value 13.8328

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 350
Mean -0.688193
Standard dev 0.559396
Max value 0.276176
Min value -1.67519

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 350
Mean 16.8575
Standard dev 0.336212
Max value 17.6573
Min value 15.7985

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 244.307

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 350
Mean 132.631
Standard dev 4.89560
Max value 140.099
Min value 123.966

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 277.798

A575 14-SEP-97 Descent From 181325-182814 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:41

A575 14-SEP-97 Descent From 181325-182814 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:41

A575 14-SEP-97 Descent From 181325-182814 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:41

A575 14--SEP--97 P8 50'--FL220 From 182814--191223 Plotted 6--May--1998 17:46

A575 14-SEP-97 P8 50'-FL220 From 182814-191223 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:47

A575 14-SEP-97 P8 50'-FL220 From 182814-191223 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:47

A575 14-SEP-97 P8 50'-FL220 From 182814-191223 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:47

A575 14-SEP-97 P8 50'-FL220 From 182814-191223 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:47

A575 14-SEP-97 P8 50'-FL220 From 182814-191223 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:47

A575 14-SEP-97 P8 50'-FL220 From 182814-191223 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:47

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 707.129
 Standard dev 172.790
 Max value 1009.80
 Min value 429.049

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 281.385
 Standard dev 11.2848
 Max value 299.979
 Min value 257.116

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 261.650
 Standard dev 21.0924
 Max value 295.767
 Min value 237.938

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 60.1783
 Standard dev 18.7119
 Max value 83.9197
 Min value 26.0346

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 4.058858e-07
 Standard dev 9.526928e-07
 Max value 4.590414e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 5.50983
 Standard dev 0.868296
 Max value 7.17259
 Min value 2.79191

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 3121.46
 Standard dev 1915.13
 Max value 6686.54
 Min value 28.7412

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 33.6767
 Standard dev 0.411778
 Max value 34.4019
 Min value 32.9947

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean -31.4364
 Standard dev 0.973402
 Max value -29.7050
 Min value -33.0277

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 14.4724
 Standard dev 1.42227
 Max value 19.4389
 Min value 11.1500

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 14.1623
 Standard dev 2.65022
 Max value 20.6945
 Min value 7.54798

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean -0.397445
 Standard dev 0.557155
 Max value 1.66745
 Min value -3.05379

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 2643
 Mean 20.3478
 Standard dev 2.23825
 Max value 25.5752
 Min value 13.7240

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 224.380

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 2644
 Mean 111.329
 Standard dev 10.2058
 Max value 130.020
 Min value 90.3095

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 63.1343

A575 14-SEP-97 P9 FL220-FL180 From 191623-192019 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:48

A575 14-SEP-97 P9 FL220-FL180 From 191623-192019 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:48

A575 14-SEP-97 P9 FL220-FL180 From 191623-192019 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:48

A575 14--SEP-97 R7 FL180 From 192019-193553 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:50

A575 14-SEP-97 R7 FL180 From 192019-193553 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:50

A575 14-SEP-97 R7 FL180 From 192019-193553 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:50

A575 14-SEP-97 R7 FL180 From 192019-193553 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:50

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 935
 Mean 507.956
 Standard dev 0.204795
 Max value 508.398
 Min value 507.449

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 935
 Mean 265.802
 Standard dev 0.639278
 Max value 266.609
 Min value 264.054

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 935
 Mean 250.470
 Standard dev 9.40811
 Max value 265.001
 Min value 238.300

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 935
 Mean 70.3312
 Standard dev 8.23750
 Max value 81.1026
 Min value 46.8679

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 935
 Mean 2.500448e-06
 Standard dev 4.687943e-06
 Max value 1.928065e-05
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 935
 Mean 1.99548
 Standard dev 0.825479
 Max value 4.05386
 Min value 0.436751

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 935
 Mean 5457.76
 Standard dev 2.98197
 Max value 5465.15
 Min value 5451.33

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 935
 Mean 34.9423
 Standard dev 0.166667
 Max value 35.2264
 Min value 34.6615

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 935
 Mean -28.4135
 Standard dev 0.365120
 Max value -27.7924
 Min value -29.0497

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 935
 Mean 12.1931
 Standard dev 1.10055
 Max value 13.7520
 Min value 8.44720

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 935
 Mean 11.2396
 Standard dev 1.39758
 Max value 13.5229
 Min value 8.24944

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 935
 Mean 0.167273
 Standard dev 0.443103
 Max value 1.76196
 Min value -0.958618

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 935
 Mean 16.6014
 Standard dev 1.59886
 Max value 18.9158
 Min value 12.1840

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 222.670

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 935
 Mean 124.398
 Standard dev 3.14002
 Max value 130.453
 Min value 118.278

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 61.3891

A575 14-SEP-97 P10 FL180-FL220 From 193553-194004 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:51

A575 14-SEP-97 P10 FL180-FL220 From 193553-194004 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:51

2 2

A575 14-SEP-97 P10 FL180-FL220 From 193553-194004 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:51

A575 14-SEP-97 P11 FL220-50' From 194004-195948 Plotted 6--May-1998 17:53

A575 14-SEP-97 P11 FL220-50' From 194004-195948 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:53

A575 14-SEP-97 P11 FL220-50' From 194004-195948 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:53

A575 14-SEP-97 R8 5000' From 200226-200701 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:54

A575 14-SEP-97 R8 5000' From 200226-200701 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:54

A575 14-SEP-97 R8 5000' From 200226-200701 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:54

A575 14-SEP-97 R8 5000' From 200226-200701 Plotted 6-May-1998 17:54

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 845.553
 Standard dev 0.941866
 Max value 846.914
 Min value 843.927

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 16.8583
 Standard dev 3.77227
 Max value 24.7946
 Min value 9.87182

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 1500.04
 Standard dev 9.07750
 Max value 1515.72
 Min value 1486.93

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 10.1544
 Standard dev 0.336924
 Max value 10.6863
 Min value 9.03696

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 11.6165
 Standard dev 0.355734
 Max value 12.2094
 Min value 10.4703

DECIDED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 288.942
 Standard dev 0.262675
 Max value 289.455
 Min value 288.435

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
 No of obs 276
 Mean 1.474622e-06
 Standard dev 2.124338e-06
 Max value 5.030022e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 36.0848
 Standard dev 9.112076e-02
 Max value 36.2441
 Min value 35.9362

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 5.62733
 Standard dev 0.419942
 Max value 6.55378
 Min value 4.76383

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 141.630
 Standard dev 10.9730
 Max value 147.718
 Min value 101.760

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 284.912
 Standard dev 1.44092
 Max value 287.027
 Min value 281.830

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
 No of obs 276
 Mean 5.437881e-04
 Standard dev 2.356701e-03
 Max value 1.072039e-02
 Min value 1.000000e-38

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 276
 Mean -25.8765
 Standard dev 8.090639e-02
 Max value -25.7371
 Min value -26.0104

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 276
 Mean -0.757632
 Standard dev 0.275905
 Max value -0.105217
 Min value -1.26963

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 35.7718

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Particle Data

- **CNC:** Condensation nucleus counter (this data is provisional and requires further validation). The measurement is from a commercial instrument: TSI INC Model 3025A. Although CNC data were recorded on the flight no post flight processing has been carried out. Rather than delay this booklet further, I have decided to wait and process the data when the validation has been carried out by the cloud physics group.
- **PSAP:** The Radiance Research Particle Soot Absorption Photometer gives a measurement of optical absorption by black carbon, using a quartz filter with the absorption measured at 565 nm.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (data not quality controlled). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using approximate scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_y) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Only one NO_y channel was available for this flight. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU.
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

ARASF

For more information contact:

**Met. Research Flight
Y46 Building, D.E.R.A.
Farnborough, Hants GU14 6TD**

Fax: +44 (0) 1252-376588

**Dr. Andrew Kaye
NERC Scientific Liaison
Tel: +44 (0) 1252-395843
E-mail: A.Kaye@nerc.ac.uk**

**Dr. Hannah Richer
Tel: +44 (0) 1252-395830
E-mail: hricher@meto.gov.uk**

**Mr. Illyea Hawke
Tel: +44 (0) 1252-395840
E-mail: idhawke@meto.gov.uk**

